

Environmental Signals which regulate and control oxidative stress induced virulence of *Vibrio cholerae*

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ABSTRACT

Vibrio cholerae is a gram negative, nonsporulating, polar, non capsulated, curve or comma-shaped rod with rounded or slightly pointed ends, about 1.5-2.4 x 0.2-0.4 μm in size. *V. cholerae* elaborates a toxin, cholera toxin, responsible for most of the diarrhoea associated with this disease. Two serogroups of *V. cholerae* – O1 and O139-cause outbreaks. *V. cholerae* O1 causes the majority of outbreaks, while O139-first identified in Bangladesh in 1992-is confined to South-East Asia. During the 19th century, cholerae spread across the world. For increasing of the strains, mutation is responsible. For this mutation, changes of virulence genes are responsible. Different environmental signals such as biofilm formation, intracellular signal, phosphate regulon, c-di-GMP, and TTSS system change the virulence gene expression. For this reason the virulence of *Vibrio cholerae* is changed by different environmental signal. Oxidative stress is produced by bacterial metabolism, the immune system and exposure to host environmental factors such as metal ions. Here they show that quorum sensing (environmental signal) enhances *V. cholerae* viability under oxidative stress condition by upregulating the expression of RpoS, and this regulation acts through HapR, suggesting that a quorum sensing oxidative stress response plays a role in *V. cholerae* environmental survival. Besides the present review briefly discusses about oxidative stress responses that have the potential to contribute to antimicrobial resistance in a variety of ways.

Keyword: Mutation, Virulence genes, Oxidative stress, Quorum sensing and antimicrobial resistance

INTRODUCTION

Cholerae, an enteric diarrheal disease caused by gram negative bacterium *Vibrio cholerae*. It is a member of the family vibriaceae. It is a facultatively anaerobic, gram negative, non spor forming curved rod, capable of respiratory and fermentative metabolism. It is an acute type of diarrheal illness that affected millions of the people around the world over the centuries. Historically, speaking, there are very few diseases that can match cholerae in terms of its severity and explosive onset in the form of an outbreak or epidemic. Further, high mortality and morbidity rates associated with classical cholerae had tremendous tragic impact on the personal as well as social life of people living in the affected areas. As a consequence, the disease had found its place in the contemporary literary works in a number of instances where subtle intricacies of human relationship were craftily dealt with in the backdrop of an ongoing epidemic. [1,3]

Differences in the sugar composition of the heat stable surface somatic “O” antigen are the basis of the serological classification of *V. cholerae* first described by Gardner and Venkatraman(1935), currently the organism is classified into 206 “O” serogroups. [4,5] Until recently, epidemic cholerae was exclusively associated with *V. cholerae* strains of the O1 serogroup. All strains that were identified as *V. cholerae* on the basis of biochemical tests but that did not agglutinate with “O” antiserum were collectively referred to as non O1 *V. cholerae*. The non O1 strains are occasionally isolated from cases of diarrhoea.

[6] and from a variety of extraintestinal infections, from wounds, and from the ear, sputum, urine, and cerebrospinal fluid.[7]

Microorganisms that biochemically resemble *V. cholerae* but lack the O1 antigen (*V. cholerae* non O1) are believed to be non-pathogenic.[8] They are widely distributed in marine environments, especially bays, estuaries and other brackish waters. It is now known, however, that some strains of the non- O1 group of *V. cholerae* are pathogens. These species have been associated with cholerae like diseases and other extraintestinal infections, not only in humans but also in higher aquatic organisms.[9] The O1 serogroup exists as two biotypes- classical and EI Tor, antigenic factors allow further differentiation into two major serotypes- ogawa and Inaba. Strains of the ogawa serotype are said to express the A and B antigens and a small amount of C antigen, whereas Inaba strains express only the A and C antigens. A third serotype (Hikojima) expresses all three antigens but is rare and unstable.

Cholerae has re-emerged as a major infectious disease in the recent past, with a global increase in its incidence. In 1994, cholerae cases were notified from 94 countries- the highest number of countries in one year(WHO). The O1 serogroup of *vibrio cholerae* is responsible for pandemic cholerae and EI Tor biotype is responsible for current cholerae pandemic. The virulence regulatory cascade in *V. cholerae* is associated

influenced by several environmental signals, which exert their effects at different levels.

Oxidative stress is a fact of everyday life for microorganisms. They encounter oxidative stress during colonization of animal hosts, even during mutualistic association such as the symbiosis. The ability of bacteria to sense and to effectively respond to changes in the environment is crucial for their survival. The role of sigma factor encoded by *rpoS* in survival following a challenge with the oxidizing agent H_2O_2 . Many types of insults to the cell envelope, caused either by physical or chemical damage, antibiotic treatment, or genetic modification induce a variety of signalling pathways that ultimately lead to common downstream consequences resulting in internal oxidative stress. The oxidative stress responses induced by O_2^- (generated intracellularly by PQ) and H_2O_2 that conferred differential adaptation of vibrio cells.

DIFFERENT VIRULENT ASSOCIATED FACTORS

Cholerae toxin-

Cholera toxin is a multisubunit ADP-ribosylating toxin that binds to GMI ganglioside found on intestinal epithelial cells. The A_1 subunit of the holotoxin activates the alpha subunit of G_s , a guanylnucleotide-binding protein involved in regulation of adenylate- cyclase activity.[10,11] ADP- ribosylation of G_s results in high levels of cAMP and subsequent alterations in ion transport in villous and crypt cells of the intestinal mucosa. The overall effect is an increase in chloride secretion into the intestinal lumen and an inhibition of sodium absorption.[12] The A and B subunits of cholera toxin are encoded by the *ctx* operon on a region of DNA termed the cTX genetic element originally thought to be a compound transposon associated with toxigenic strains of *Vibrio cholerae*. [13] It is now known that the *ctx* genes lie within the genome of a lysogenic filamentous phage(cTX ϕ). The single stranded cTX ϕ infects *V.cholerae* by absorbing to the toxin coregulated pilus(TCP) which is major colonization determinant of *V.cholerae*. Upon infection of *V.cholerae* the cTX ϕ genome integrates into the genome of *V.cholerae*. The 6.9 kb cTX ϕ genome has a modular structure composed of two distinct domain the core and RS2 region. The core region encodes cholerae toxin and phage morphogenesis genes. RS2 encodes genes required for regulation of CTX ϕ . [14] Comparative analysis of CTX ϕ from a number of *V.cholerae* strains indicate that acquisition of this phage by vibrio sp.has occurred multiple times and has involved several CTX ϕ genotypes.[15]

Toxin coregulated pilus-

The type IV pillus encoded by *V.cholerae* was named toxin coregulated pillus because its production parallels that of cholera toxin.[16] The TCP structure is assembled as a polymer of repeating subunits of TCPA pilin that form long fibers, which associate into bundles. Production of TCP on the vibrio surface leads to autoagglutination of the cells. In vitro and in vivo analysis of *tcpA* mutants suggest that a major function of TCP is to mediate vibrio interaction through direct pilus-pilus contact which leads to microcolony formation, intestinal colonization and increased serum resistance.[17] As it is the case for the *ctxAB* genes, *V.cholerae* *tcpA* and TCP biogenesis genes are encoded by a genetic element with the characteristics of a phage.[18,19] Thus it appears that the two major virulence determinants of *V.cholerae*, which are co-ordinately expressed in response to a regulatory cascade that is influenced in vivo signals.

Accessory colonization factor-

Intestinal mucus provides a chemotactic signal for *V.cholerae* whereby the vibrios direct their movement toward the intestinal surface. Directed motility coupled with the vibrios ability to secrete enzymes(mucinase, lipases, proteinases) capable of degrading mucus, maximize the ability of *V.cholerae* to burrow through the mucus to the surface of intestinal cells.[20] Disruption of ACF(accessory colonization factor) genes results in altered swarm plate phenotypes which is characteristic of genes involved in chemotaxis.[21]

ToxR/ToxS regulon-

ToxR encodes a 32KDa integral membrane protein that contains a cytoplasmically located amino terminal domain related to several prokaryotic transcriptional activators. The expression of ToxR regulon is controlled by a cascade of regulatory proteins (ToxR, TcpP and ToxT). The carboxy-terminus domain lies within the periplasmic space and is thought to be involved in sensing specific environmental conditions. It has been proposed that the ToxR periplasmic domain senses osmolarity and is able to adapt a conformation that promotes transcriptional activator. A role of osmolarity in this process comes from a study in which the ToxR periplasmic domain was replaced with alkaline phosphatase. The ToxR-alkaline phosphatase fusion protein was able to activate *ctxAB* expression but was insensitive to high osmolarity, an in vitro growth condition that normally represses *ctxAB* expression.[22] This observation makes sense since ToxR is an 'ancestral' gene that is present in other *vibrio* species which is involved in modulating OmpT and OmpU outer membrane protein levels in responses to different salinity levels found in the environment. This suggests that ToxR/ToxS act as direct mediators of signal transduction via their ability to recognize environmental signals.

ToxT-

It is a homologue of a large family of positive regulators referred to as AraC/xlyS family. *toxT* expression is controlled by environmental signals.*toxT* transcription is activated by ToxR and TcpP in response to various medium conditions that is temperature,osmolarity,and p^H . Its expression regulates cholerae toxin, toxin coregulated pilus and accessory colonization factor synthesis.[23]

TcpP/TcpH-

The expression of *tcpH* is influenced by temperature and p^H in similar fashion to that of *ctx* and *tcp*, two genes further down the regulatory cascade.[24] These data indicate that ToxR/ToxS, TcpP and TcpH represent a membrane bound transcriptional regulation complex that activates gene expression in response to particular environmental signals.

AphA/AphB-

Recent study identified two genes *aphA* and *aphB*(activator of *tcpP* and *tcpH* expression) that are required for maximum expression of *tcpP*. [25,26] *AphA* and *AphB* may function in recognition and transduction of environmental signals required for proper ToxR regulon activation.

DIFFERENT ENVIRONMENTAL SIGNALS controls/regulates the virulence of *Vibrio cholerae*

Biofilm formation-

Biofilm is an assemblage of the microbial cells that is irreversibly associated with a surface and usually enclosed in a matrix of polysaccharide material. It is followed by attachment, foration of microcolonies and finally the formation of the mature three

dimensional biofilm structure with characteristic pillars and water channels. *Vibrio cholerae* biofilms are more resistant to stresses such as antibiotics, chlorine.[27] A number of regulatory factors are involved in VPS (*Vibrio* exopolysaccharide) expression and biofilm formation, and one of the driving signals behind biofilm formation is increased expression of the signalling molecule c-di-GMP.[28,29] Elevated levels of c-di-GMP drive *Vibrio cholerae* toward enhanced VPS expression and down regulate motility and virulence gene expression.[30]

Effect of extracellular phosphate on VPS expression and biofilm formation-

Vibrio cholerae build stores of intracellular polyphosphate(poly-p). The enzyme polyphosphate kinase (PPk) is responsible for the synthesis of poly-p from ATP. Cholerae PPK mutant exhibits a reduced capacity to withstand conditions of low P^H, high salinity and oxidative stress in low phosphate medium. These findings underline the importance of phosphate homeostasis as well as sensing and responding to changes in extracellular phosphate in the *Vibrio cholerae* life cycle. In *E.coli*, deprivation of phosphate induces the expression of the *phoB* regulon.[31] *PhoR* is an inner membrane histidine kinase that responds to periplasmic orthophosphate through its interaction with the phosphate transport system. Under conditions of phosphate limitation, phosphorus is transferred from phospho-*phoR* to the response regulator *PhoB*. Phospho-*PhoB* then binds to DNA *pho* boxes to activate or repress the transcription of target genes. In addition, *phoB* negatively regulates biofilm formation in *Vibrio cholerae* of classical and El Tor biotypes.[32,33] *VPSR*(positive regulator) has an essential function in biofilm formation by acting as a receiver of external carbon and phosphorus sensory information to modulate biosynthesis of the exopolysaccharide matrix.

Motility factors and virulence-

Vibrio cholerae virulence has been linked to motility. An inverse relationship between motility and virulence had been suggested by the observation that spontaneous hypermotile mutants express almost no CT(cholera toxin) or TCP(toxin coregulated pilus), while spontaneous non-motile mutants express increased levels of CT and TCP.[34] Utilizing whole genome transcription profiling of *V.cholerae* strains with mutations in the key flagellar regulatory genes(*rpoN*, *flrA*, *flrC*, and *fliA*), it was observed that non-flagellated strains exhibit increased transcription of known (CT, TCP) and virulence factors(*T6SS*, hemolysins).[35] Hyper swarming vibrio cells were found to be defective in TCP synthesis, toxin production and production of a cell associated hemolysin while non-motile vibrios demonstrated increased expression of these virulence genes.[36] Thus there is an inverse relationship between motility and virulence factor expression.

Intercellular signaling-

It is a mechanism by which binding of an extracellular signal molecule to a cell surface receptor triggers a response inside the cell. Quorum sensing is a process by which bacteria communicate with one another by secreting extracellular signaling molecules termed autoinducers. Production of virulence factors by *Vibrio cholerae* is strongly influenced by environmental conditions. The *ToxR* regulon signal transduction cascade is responsible for sensing and integrating a complex amount of environmental information in order to spatially and temporally coordinate virulence gene expression. It was discovered that in addition to the known components of the *ToxR* signaling circuit, quorum sensing regulation is involved in virulence gene expression.[37] Besides,

LuxO and *HapR* were also shown to regulate motility, protease production and biofilm formation. Quorum sensing mediate repression of *Vibrio* virulence genes. In *V.cholerae*, two autoinducer/ sensor systems have been identified. System1 consists of cholerae autoinducer1 (CAI-1,3-hydroxytridecane-4-one), synthesized by the activity of *cqsA*, and its cognate receptor, *CqsS*.[38,39] System 2 consists of an AI-2 molecule(a furanosyl borate di-ester), synthesized by the activity of *LuxS*, and its cognate receptor, *LuxPQ*.[40] The third quorum sensing system was predicted by Miller.et.al in 2002 but deletion mutants grew.

CsrA is part of the third quorum sensing system in V.cholerae:

CsrA is also found in *V.cholerae* and has been shown to have similar global control as in *E.coli*. In this study, it was shown that there was a third quorum sensing system and that it is controlled by *csrA* along with three small RNAs called *csrB*,*C*, and *D*. This system is initiated by *varS* and *varA*. *VarS* activates *VarA*. Active *VarA* causes the transcription of three sRNAs called *csrB*,*csrC* and *csrD*. These sRNAs bind to and inactivate *csrA* protein.

C-di-GMP(bis-3'5'cyclic-dimeric-guanosine monophosphate)

The second messenger, cyclic diguanylic acid regulates the motile lifestyle by activating biofilm formation and inhibiting motility. Cyclic-di-GMP is synthesized from GTP by GGDEF domain family proteins that exhibit diguanylate cyclase(DGC) activity. The *V.cholerae* genome contains 31 genes encoding GGDEF domain family proteins, 10 genes encoding proteins with GGDEF and EAL domains,12 genes encoding proteins with only EAL domains, and 9 genes encoding proteins with HD-GYP domains.[41] Transcriptional profiling has revealed that genes involved in flagellum biosynthesis, motility and chemotaxis are repressed in response to an increase in intracellular c-di-GMP.[42] The signaling pathways is responsible for the phenotypic consequences of increasing the c-di-GMP pool. The positive regulator of biofilm formation, *VPST*, can directly senses c-di-GMP to modulate motility and biofilm formation.[43] Finally, there are two riboswitches responsive to c-di-GMP changes in the *V.cholerae* genome.[44]

TTSS(type three secretion system):

The type three secretion system(TTSS) is a major virulence factors. The TTSS mediates translocation of toxins from the bacteria directly into the eukaryotic host cell. Its function in several gram negative enteric pathogens. *TDH*(important secreted toxin) expression is regulated by a *toxR* and in *Vibrio cholerae* o1 strains, *ToxR* controls expression of virulence factors(such as TCP,and CT) and other less characterized genes.[45] Thus *TDH* is regulated by *ToxR*, and secreted by the TTSS in *Vibrio cholerae* strains that carry these genes. The prevalence and diversity of non O1 and non O139 strains in the environment, acquisition of a TTSS may represent one of the several strategies that *V.cholerae* employs to compete for survival within its various niches. It is therefore interest that O141 strains carry the TTSS genes because this serogroups is unusual in having a global distribution and a clonal phylogeny.[46] Thus it is possible that the TTSS system in *V.cholerae* may be critical for environmental fitness and therefore for pandemic spread. AM-19226(non-O139 strain) carries a type III secretion system(TTSS) that is related to a *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* TTSS gene cluster.[47] Preliminary annotation of the AM-19226 sequence revealed numerous potential virulence genes based on homology to genes in other bacterial species, including those involved in biogenesis of type IV pili and several

toxins. In particular, contig 247 was found to carry nine genes predicted to encode proteins with significant similarity to the functional component of TTSS.[48] TTSS genes encoding all of the essential components of the needle complex that typically is required for the delivery of TTSS effector proteins into target eukaryotic cells.[49]

Phosphate regulon(PHO)-

Phosphate is an essential nutrient for all life. Both aquatic and terrestrial environments are generally through to be limiting for phosphate. Therefore, bacteria and other microorganism must actively pursue phosphate. One method, bacteria have developed to acquire phosphate is the phosphate specific transport (pst) system. The pst system is a high affinity inorganic phosphate transporter. The pst system is composed of five components encoded within the pst SCAB- phou operon. In addition to the pi transport function, the pst system has also been shown to be a regulator of the two component system, PhoR. PhoR is a histidine kinase known to phosphorylate the response regulator PhoB in conditions of low environmental pi, in turn phospho-PhoB regulates transcription of a large gene set, known as the Pho regulon, generally involved in phosphate homeostasis. By some mechanism the activation of PhoB is blocked by the pst system when environmental pi is in excess. However, when pi is limiting this repression is relieved, thus allowing induction of the Pho regulon. Null mutations in the pst genes disrupt regulation of phoB activation, which leads to expression of the Pho regulon, regardless of environmental phosphate availability.[50]

phoB (pho regulon) regulates virulence gene expression in *Vibrio cholerae*:

The expression of the core virulence determinants CT and TCP in Δ pst, Δ phoB and Δ pst Δ phoB during growth in virulence gene inducing conditions (M9 minimal medium supplemented with amino acids N,R,E and S at 30°C). Expression of CT was measured by western blot against the CT-B subunit and was shown to be defective in Δ pst, while Δ phoB showed no change in expression compared with wild type(Fig.1A). Mutation of Δ phoB in the pst background led to restoration of CT-B expression to near wild-type levels, suggesting that phoB regulates expression of CT. The expression of TCP in each strain by measuring transcription of tcpA, the major subunit of TCP, using qRT-PCR. Δ phoB had no effect, but Δ pst showed approximately five fold reduction in tcpA expression. Mutation of phoB in the Δ pst background restored tcpA expression to wild type levels(Fig.1B). For expression of both CT and TCP, the Δ pst Δ phoB phenotypes could not be fully complemented by expression of phoB in trans, presumably due to incorrect phoB expression level. However, the phenotypes were complemented by reversion of the phoB mutation, restoring the original defective virulence gene expression of Δ pst. This showed that the mutant phenotypes of the Δ pst and Δ phoB strains were not due to secondary mutations.

CT and TCP are regulated by a complex cascade of virulence activators, known as the ToxR regulon). The expression of the direct regulator of TCP and CT expression, ToxT, was reduced in Δ pst approximately fivefold compared with wild type, and that the defect was eliminated in Δ pst Δ phoB. The expression of direct regulators of toxT, TcpP and ToxR, by qRT-PCR. There is no change in toxR transcription in any mutant strain tested. To confirm that the activity of ToxR was no altered by activation of phoB, the expression of OmpU, another ToxR regulated protein, by western blot. There is no observe a change in OmpU

expression in any strain tested, suggesting that ToxR activity is not affected by phoB.

The expression of known direct regulators of tcpP transcription, aphA, aphB and crp, but there is no observe any changes in transcription. Therefore, the phoB negatively regulates virulence gene expression by repressing the tcpPH promoter.

Fig.1 phoB regulates virulence gene expression in *V. cholerae*. *Vibrio cholerae* strains were grown in M9+NRES at 30°C.

phoB negatively regulates expression of the two major virulence determinants of *V. cholerae*, TCP and CT. This is in contrast to a previous report, which concluded that PhoB does not regulate CT expression (Von Kruger et.al., 1999). The pst mutant allowed to study the role of phoB in virulence gene regulation using standard in vitro virulence gene inducing

conditions, rather than altering the phosphate concentration in these conditions in order to activate phoB. Modifying the phosphate concentration changes the growth conditions, the physiology of *V. cholerae* and alters virulence gene induction. phoB interferes with the function of the RNA polymerase at the tcpPH promoter, by disrupting its interaction with AphB, preventing RNA polymerase binding to the promoter or blocking initiation of transcription. This makes a novel connection between phosphate homeostasis and virulence gene regulation in *Vibrio cholerae*.

Oxidative stress and *Vibrio cholerae*-

Oxidative stress occurs in an organism when reactive oxygen intermediates (ROI_s) are present in higher concentration than what can be detoxified efficiently by the cellular defence mechanisms. This leads to a decline in bacterial fitness or even death. The most prevalent of these radicals are the superoxide radicals (O₂⁻), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and hydroxyl radical (OH).

Oxidative stress is produced by bacterial metabolism, the immune system and exposure to host environmental factors such as metal ions. Oxidative stress induces damage to DNA, proteins, membranes and can lead to cell death. Organisms that grow aerobically are routinely exposed to oxidative stress in the form of reactive oxygen species (ROS_s) [e.g-peroxide, superoxide(SO)] that are the unavoidable by products of aerobic respiration. ROS_s damage a variety of cellular macromolecules and thus elicit

adaptive oxidative stress responses in bacteria intended to permit survival in the presence of stressor.

Efficient killing of *Vibrios* by host macrophages depends on a number of mechanisms including production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) by the phagosomal NADPH oxidase. ROS like superoxide radical, hydrogen peroxide, and hydroxyl radical are toxic compound produced by the incomplete reduction of oxygen during oxidative metabolism.[51] These compounds are cytotoxic oxidants that can initiate lipid peroxidation, cause DNA strand breaks and oxidize organic molecules, leading to cell damage or death. Cells have acquired relevant protective mechanisms to maintain the lowest possible levels of ROS inside the cell. The protective mechanisms include both non enzymatic (ascorbic acid, β carotene, glutathione and α -tocopherol) and enzymatic (superoxide dismutase[SOD], catalase[CAT] and glutathione peroxidase[GP_X] antioxidant system. Bacteria employ mainly enzyme mechanisms to eliminate the damaging effects of oxidative stress such as superoxide dismutase, NADH oxidase, CAT, GP_X , glutathione reductase, thiol peroxidase and alkyl hydroperoxidase.

Quorum sensing (environmental signal) enhances the oxidative stress response in *Vibrio cholerae*:

Oxidative stress in animals have been found under different environmental conditions when they are fed on different drinks.[52,54] It has been shown that RPO_S is important in *V.cholerae* resistance to oxidative and nutritional stresses, both of which *V.cholerae* may encounter in its marine habitat.[55,57] It has previously reported that quorum sensing enhances the survival rate of bacteria under certain stress conditions.[58] They tested wild type E1 TorC6706 and a number of quorum sensing mutants for their ability to respond to oxidative stress via exposure to H₂O₂. H₂O₂ was chosen as an oxidative stressor because of its presence and importance in two of *V.cholerae* 's reservoirs as an antimicrobial factor in the human intestine and its occurrence in *V.cholerae* ' s aquatic reservoirs.[59] The luxO and luxS mutants were also unaffected by the addition of H₂O₂, while the remaining strains showed a much higher sensitivity to this stressor within 30 min of exposure .The luxO constitutive mutants and cqsA mutants, all showing high sensitivity to H₂O₂, have been shown to be deficient in quorum sensing regulation because of a tight repression of this system.[60] The luxO-null mutant, which survived as well as the wild-type strain in this assay, exhibits a constitutive upregulated quorum sensing system.[61] The luxS mutant also showed resistance to H₂O₂ , and this gene has been shown to be dispensable in the regulation of the quorum sensing cascade.[62] Oxidative stress resistance was completely rescued to wild type levels when the cqsA mutant was grown under the condition.

Because the quorum sensing mutants sensitive to the oxidative stress assay have been documented as being deficient in HapR production, they performed a western blot analysis to examine the production patterns of this protein at late-log phase(immediately before the addition of H₂O₂ in the H₂O₂ stress response assay) growth in these strains. Equal amounts of total protein of late log cultures were size fractionated by sodium dodecyl sulphate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis, transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane, and detected with affinity-purified polyclonal anti HapR rabbit anti-serum. The results confirm that the strains exhibiting a deficiency in response to H₂O₂ had a negative HapR phenotype under the conditions of the stress response assay. These

results suggest that HapR plays an important role in enhancing the *V.cholerae* response to oxidative stress.

They repeated the oxidative stress response experiment with the wild type and hapR mutant strains to confirm HapR's role in stress response. They also introduced each strain with either a plasmid containing ptac-hapR or vector control pBBR1-MCS2.[63]

Characterize the role of quorum sensing in the stress response, they tested the viability of hapR wild type and mutant strains under a low nutrient stress condition in artificial sea water.[64] They found that the expression of the stress response regulator RPO_S in the wild type was three fold more than that of the hapR mutant under these conditions. RPO_S has been shown to be critical in *V.cholerae* for survival under oxidative and nutritional stresses,[65] and thus they hypothesized that quorum sensing enhanced stress responses acts through the regulation of rpoS.

The rpoS mutant strains showed a much higher sensitivity to H₂O₂ than their RpoS wild type counterparts, as has been previously reported,[66] regardless of whether HapR was present. This indicates that HapR alone does not mediate this response directly but through the action of RpoS. These data confirm that RpoS is critical for the oxidative stress response in *V.cholerae* and that HapR may enhance this response directly through RpoS.

In this study in *V.cholerae* they have shown that quorum sensing signaling system acting through HapR enhances the expression of rpoS and resistance to stress. The fact that RpoS can also active hapR expression[67] highlights the possible importance of a HapR/RpoS autoregulation loop in the fact of environmental stressors. A possible outcome of this is that this interaction of quorum sensing and the stress response may play a survival role in biofilm associated cells in *V.cholerae*'s natural environment.

Oxidative stress responses have the potential to contribute to antimicrobial resistance in a variety of ways-

Redox-responsive regulators of multidrug efflux system-

SoxRS, originally defined as an SO-responsive TCS that controls an adaptive SO stress response, since it was activated by redox-cycling agents (e.g. paraquat) that generated SO inside aerobically growing cells,[68] is now known to respond directly to these redox-cycling agents.[69] As univalent oxidants, these agents can, however, directly oxidize SoxR (to activate the SoxRS regulon), although their major toxic activities may well have to do with depletion of cellular NADPH, and thus interference with NADPH-requiring biosynthetic processes (i.e. SoxRS may be responding to a form of metabolic stress).[70] Nonetheless, an important component of the protective SoxRS-mediated response to redox-cycling agents is the AcrAB-TolC multidrug efflux system, with acrAB expression positively regulated by SoxS[71] in response to redox-cycling agents in *E. Coli* [72]. Mutations leading to constitutive soxS expression and elevated acrAB expression and antimicrobial resistance have been described in laboratory and/or clinical isolates of *E. Coli*.[73] SoxS also controls expression of the siRNA micF, whose expression reduces OmpF translation, with reduction of this OM porin serving to promote antimicrobial resistance by limiting antimicrobial uptake.[74] Although few studies have examined the impact of SoxRS-responsive stresses on antimicrobial resistance, paraquat has been shown to enhance resistance of *E. coli* to enoxacin, dependent upon SoxRS,[75] although the contribution of AcrAB-TolC to this was not examined. Redox-cycling agents have also been shown to induce SoxRS-dependent expression of the LPS core biosynthetic locus waaYZ in *E. coli*, where WaaY

functions in the phosphorylation of core heptose residues.[76] A number of additional regulators of multidrug efflux systems respond to oxidative stress, including MexR, the repressor of the mexAB-oprM multidrug efflux operon of *P. aeruginosa*:[77] MgrA, the global regulator in *S. aureus* that regulates 300 genes, including the major facilitator (MF) family antimicrobial efflux genes norA, norB and tet38:[78] and SarZ, an MgrA functional homologue that regulates several genes in *S. aureus*, including the norB and tet38 efflux genes.[79] Thus oxidative stress might be expected to enhance efflux gene expression.

Antibiotic-dependent oxidative stress-protective mechanisms:

Given the observation that ROSs (i.e. .OH) and the oxidative stress that results from antimicrobial exposure are generally associated with the lethal effects of bactericidal antimicrobials.[80,81] Antioxidant/oxidative stress-protective responses in bacteria would promote antimicrobial resistance. Certainly elimination of ROS defence genes in *E. coli* has been correlated with increased antimicrobial susceptibility.[82] A possible oxidative stress protective mechanism that promotes antimicrobial resistance in *E. coli* involves indole, an extracellular signalling molecule whose production is promoted by exposure to antimicrobials[83] and, possibly, oxidative stress—ROSs induce the *tnaA* tryptophanase gene whose product catalyses the synthesis of indole.[84] Environmental stress conditions can impact NO production, and thus antimicrobial resistance in this organism. Bacterial production of another gas, H₂S, has also been linked recently to antimicrobial resistance—deletion of genes for H₂S synthesis in *Bacillus anthracis*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli* rendered cells susceptible to multiple antimicrobials.[85] Regulation of H₂S production and /or activity/expression of H₂S synthetic proteins/genes was not assessed, so it is not yet clear whether this antimicrobial resistance mechanism will be impacted by environmental growth (i.e. stress) conditions. Antioxidant strategies are, nonetheless, clearly important for antimicrobial resistance in bacteria, and thus environmental conditions that activate protective antioxidant genes/enzymes will promote antimicrobial resistance. Polyamines also contribute to resistance to ROSs in *E. coli*, both in functioning as antioxidants[86] and in promoting expression of antioxidant/oxidative stress-protective genes.[87-88] Recently a modest positive impact of antibiotics on polyamine production was seen in *E. coli*, and this appeared to alleviate, to some extent, antimicrobial-dependent ROS production and render cells less susceptible to antimicrobials.

CONCLUSION

The review describes about the different environmental signals that regulates the virulence and oxidative stress responses of *Vibrio cholerae*. Different environmental signals such as biofilm formation, motility factors, intercellular signal, c-di-GMP, TTSS, phosphate regulon – change a group of virulence gene expression and quorum sensing (environmental signal) enhances the oxidative stress response in *Vibrio cholerae* . This oxidative stress responses have the potential to change the virulence of *Vibrio cholerae* in variety of ways. . Modifying the phosphate concentration changes the growth conditions, the physiology of *V.cholerae* and alters the virulence gene induction. *phoB* interferes with the function of the RNA polymerase at the *tcpPH* promoter, by disrupting its interaction with *AphB*, preventing RNA polymerase binding to the promoter or blocking initiation of transcription. This finding makes a novel connection between phosphate homeostasis and virulence gene

regulation in *V.cholerae*. Expression of the major virulence factors is controlled by a cascade of regulatory proteins. This study show about the relationship between motility and virulence factors. This study describes about a number of regulatory factors that are involved in biofilm formation and one of the driving signals behind biofilm formation is increased expression of the signaling molecule c-di-GMP. Thus different environmental signals are essential factors required for virulence gene expression throughout the entire life cycle of *Vibrio cholerae* .

Besides , this study show that quorum sensing (environmental signal) enhances *V.cholerae* viability under certain stress conditions by upregulating the expression of RpoS, and this regulation acts through HapR, suggesting that a quorum sensing enhanced oxidative stress response plays a role in *V.cholerae* environmental survival. This review demonstrated that exposure to paraquat (PQ) caused induction of reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as superoxide anion radical (O₂⁻) and H₂O₂. At this same time , second stress factor significantly inhibited superoxide anion radical production and enhanced the intracellular H₂O₂ content. The enhanced ROS generation resulted in a increase in the levels of oxidatively damaged proteins. The present review briefly discusses about the oxidative stress responses that have the potential to change the different regulatory gene expression in variety of ways.

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List of Abbreviation Used-

WHO- World Health Organization
 cAMP- Cyclic adenosine monophosphate
 TCP- Toxin coregulated pilus
 ACF- Aberrant crypt foci
 VPS- Vibrio exopolysaccharide
 PPK- Polyphosphate kinase
 CT- Cholerae toxin
 GTP- Guanosine 5'- triphosphate
 TDH- Thermostable Direct Hemolysin
 ROI_s- Reactive oxygen intermediate
 ROS_s- Reactive oxygen species
 DGC- Diguanylate cyclase activity
 C-di-GMP- bis-3'5' cyclic-dimeric-guanosine monophosphate
 TTSS- type three secretion system

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